
Contribution to the public consultation on the
Commission's draft measures in DMA.100220 –
Consultation on the proposed measures for
interoperability with Google Android
(Article 6(7) of the DMA)

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Responsible according to European press law:
Matthias Kirschner / FSFE e.V.
Revalerstr. 19
10405 Berlin
Germany

Contributors:
Dario Presutti
Jithendra Palepu
Lucas Lasota

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Free Software Foundation Europe (FSFE) welcomes the European Commission's draft measures under Article 6(7) of the Digital Markets Act concerning interoperability obligations for Google Android (Case DMA.100220). We support the Commission's recognition that meaningful interoperability requires non-discriminatory access to the technical capabilities through which gatekeepers deploy AI-driven functionalities.

We identify four areas requiring strengthening. First, the measures must address uninstallability: so long as Alphabet's AI components can be silently reinstalled after removal, effective interoperability remains illusory. Second, the obligations must explicitly extend beyond Google's controlled technical stack to cover Android-based operating systems (Android Distributions) that do not depend on Google Mobile Services. Third, the developer verification framework in Paragraph 134 structurally excludes alternative Android Distributions who operate outside any contractual relationship with Alphabet. These are precisely the actors the DMA's interoperability obligations are designed to empower, and any verification process routed through Google's commercial infrastructure is incompatible with the regulation's objectives. Fourth, the free-of-charge requirements in Paragraphs 139 and 145 must explicitly prohibit Google account and developer agreement requirements as instruments of indirect access conditioning.

GLOSSARY

- AOSP - Android Open Source Project: the publicly available, Free and Open Source codebase maintained by Google that forms the technical foundation of the Android operating system.
- “Android custom/alternative ROMs” or “Android Distributions”: alternative versions of the Android operating system based on AOSP without Google’s middleware. For the purpose of this submission, the terms are used as synonyms. They are referred to as “Android Distributions”.
- “Google” and “Alphabet”: Google is part of the Alphabet Inc. holding conglomerate, founded in 2015. As the operations remain principally with Google, this paper refers to Google and the holding level Alphabet Inc. interchangeably.

INTRODUCTION

The [Free Software Foundation Europe \(FSFE\)](#) is a non-profit organisation dedicated to empowering users to control technology through Free Software. Our work includes longstanding engagement on [Device Neutrality](#), the principle that users should be able to run the operating system and install and uninstall software of their choice, free from any restrictions, on the devices they own.

The FSFE has a long track record of engagement in regulatory proceedings relevant to software freedom and platform contestability, including under the Digital Markets Act. Most recently, we [contributed](#) to the European Commission's public consultation on Apple's interoperability specifications (DMA.100204).

The FSFE welcomes the Commission's draft measures under Article 6(7) of Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 in Case DMA.100220 concerning interoperability obligations for Google Android. The proposed measures represent an important step towards addressing structural asymmetries in the Android ecosystem, particularly in relation to AI assistants, on-device models, contextual intelligence systems, background execution, and access to system-level functionalities. In particular, the draft recognises that effective interoperability in modern mobile ecosystems increasingly depends not merely on formal API availability, but on meaningful and non-discriminatory access to the technical capabilities, resources, and integration pathways through which gatekeepers deploy AI-driven functionalities across the operating system environment.

We recognise that today, few Free Software projects are in a position to request access to the AI-related interoperability features covered by the draft measures. These are resource-constrained communities, often volunteer-driven, that operate deliberately outside the commercial infrastructure of the

Google's Android ecosystem. But the rules established now will govern access for years to come. If the framework the Commission mandates presupposes a contractual relationship with Alphabet or is scoped only to Google-certified devices, Free Software developers and alternative Android distributors will find themselves structurally excluded, not because they fail any technical criterion, but because the framework was not designed with them in mind. The FSFE therefore urges the Commission to ensure that the interoperability obligations it establishes are technically neutral, contractually unconditional, and open to the full range of legitimate actors, including those who are not yet here to ask for it.

SECTION 5: MEASURES FOR ALL FEATURES

Uninstallation of AI-based features

Paragraph 125 and 126 – On User consent and Uninstallability

The Commission should clarify that effective interoperability also requires effective uninstallability. The draft measures rightly recognise that AI assistants, on-device models, contextual intelligence systems, and background execution capabilities are becoming structural parts of the Android environment, particularly through the measures on context-aware intelligence, system-level on-device models, on-device model implementation, and background execution¹. However, if Alphabet's own AI components remain persistently installed, privileged, automatically updated, or reinstalled after deletion, users will not have real control over their devices. Commission should furthermore clarify that the interoperability obligations must extend beyond

¹ Sections 2.3, 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3; paragraphs 39-47, 94-111, and 112-120 of the draft measures.

Google-controlled implementations of Android and function across the broader AOSP ecosystem.

Sections 5.1 and 5.9 of the draft measures already move in this direction by requiring implementation across the Google Android ecosystem and by seeking to avoid fragmentation.² However, the measures should expressly state that interoperability solutions must remain usable and implementable on Android-based operating systems that do not depend on Google Mobile Services or other proprietary Google components. Otherwise, there is a risk that interoperability formally exists only within a Google-controlled technical stack, thereby undermining the DMA's objectives of contestability and device neutrality.

This is particularly important in the context of AI assistants and on-device AI functionality. Effective interoperability should enable the development and deployment of fully independent AI assistants and AI services on Android-based operating systems while preserving application compatibility. The measures should therefore be implemented in a technologically neutral manner that does not presuppose continued dependence on Google services, Google accounts, proprietary APIs, or Google-controlled implementation paths. Such an approach would also be consistent with the Commission's own interpretation of Article 6(7) DMA in the Apple interoperability specification proceedings (DMA.100203), where the Commission clarified that gatekeepers cannot impose their own model of security and privacy on third parties and that "the choice whether to use a service should be the prerogative of the end user, not of the gatekeeper controlling the operating system." The same principle should apply in the context of AI systems integrated into Android.

² Paragraphs 122–124, 150–151

If Alphabet's own AI components remain persistently installed, privileged, automatically updated, or reinstalled after deletion, users will not have real control over their devices. Google Chrome's silent download and reinstallation of Gemini Nano-like model files illustrate the risk: AI functionality can be pushed onto user devices as infrastructure, without meaningful prior consent, and then treated as a default part of the computing environment. This would undermine the DMA's objectives of contestability, fairness, and user autonomy.

The measures should therefore state that users must be able to fully disable, uninstall, delete, and replace all Alphabet's AI-related components. This choice must be persistent: once a user removes or disables such functionality, Alphabet should not reinstall, reactivate, or update it unless the user gives new explicit consent. This is also important from the perspective of storage space, device resources, and practical usability.

As previously highlighted in our [DMA review submission](#) in relation to Article 6(3) DMA, and in a [complaint](#) to the European Commission submitted in July 2025, uninstallability must mean actual deletion, including the recovery of storage space necessary to install and use competing software. The same principle should apply to AI infrastructure and downloaded on-device models, which can occupy substantial device resources while remaining difficult or impossible for users to meaningfully remove.

Interoperability and AOSP

Paragraphs 122, 123, 124 – On Android interoperability

The Commission should furthermore clarify that the interoperability obligations must extend beyond Google controlled implementations of Android and function across the broader AOSP ecosystem.

Sections 5.1 and 5.9 of the draft measures already move in this direction by requiring implementation across the Google Android ecosystem and by seeking to avoid fragmentation.¹ However, the measures should expressly state that interoperability solutions must remain usable and implementable on Android-based operating systems that do not depend on Google Mobile Services or other proprietary Google components. Otherwise, there is a risk that interoperability formally exists only within a Google-controlled environment, thereby undermining the DMA's objectives.

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Decoupling interoperability from Google Developer Verification

Paragraph 134 – On Developer Verification

We acknowledge the Commission's effort in regulating Google's developer verification requirements, and welcome the attention the draft measures pay to the concerns raised by Android developer communities and end-users through the global [Keep Android Open](#) campaign. This campaign, supported by developers, researchers, and civil society groups across multiple continents, highlighted how Google's verification and certification requirements can operate as gatekeeping mechanisms rather than mere quality controls. In practice, access to core platform features becomes tied to participation in Google's commercial ecosystem. The Commission's willingness to engage with those concerns and subject the verification framework to regulatory constraints is a meaningful step forward. However, as we set out below, the draft measures do not yet go far enough and as drafted the measure is ambiguous and could be exploited by Alphabet.

We understand Paragraph 134 as setting limitations and conditions on access on a verification or registration process that must, among other things, "apply only on the Google Play Store". However, we are concerned that this wording will give way to tying this verification *with* accessing the features from Google as specified in this Annex. This single condition is sufficient to disqualify an entire category of legitimate beneficiaries: developers and distributors of alternative Android-based operating systems, commonly referred to as alternative Android Distributions, who have no contractual relationship with Google, do not distribute software through the Google Play Store, and have affirmatively structured their projects to operate outside Google's contractual ecosystem. This is not an oversight. It is the defining characteristic of those projects. Requiring them to submit to a Google-operated or Google-Play-

mediated verification process as a precondition for accessing interoperability features is equivalent to conditioning their access on abandoning the independence that makes them a meaningful competitive alternative to Google's own Android distribution.

Alternative Android Distributions represent the most direct form of platform-level competition to Google Android. They are not third-party apps running on top of Google's platform. They are alternative implementations of the platform itself. They are precisely the category of competitor that the DMA's interoperability obligations are designed to empower. Any verification mechanism that excludes them, whether by requiring Play Store presence, Android developer verification, Android compatibility certification, or any other credential that presupposes a commercial or contractual relationship with Alphabet, is incompatible with the fundamental objectives of this regulation.

Alternative Android Distributions' developers and distributors usually do not sign any agreement in Google's standard contractual stack for Android ecosystem participants. This is intentional: those agreements impose obligations, including mandatory pre-installation of Google services, placement requirements, and restrictions on forking, that are incompatible with the independence these projects exist to provide. Entering into such agreements would not merely be commercially burdensome; it would in many cases be structurally incompatible with the projects' architecture, governance, and often their open-source licensing.

The consequence is that paragraph 134, as it currently stands, is ambiguous and can be exploited negatively. It creates a class of beneficiaries, those without any contractual relationship with Google, who cannot access the verification process at all, not because they fail any objective technical criterion, but because the process itself is routed through Google's commercial

infrastructure. This is not a gap that can be remedied by improving the verification process. It can only be remedied by eliminating the requirement that access be mediated through that infrastructure.

Therefore, we urge the Commission to amend Paragraph with the following:

"Alphabet shall make the features in Sections 1–4 of this Annex, and all interoperability solutions implementing those features, accessible to all developers and distributors without any prior authorisation, registration, or verification process. Access may not be conditioned on: holding a Google developer account of any tier; distributing software through the Google Play Store; having entered into any agreement with Alphabet or any of its affiliates; or holding Android compatibility certification. Alphabet shall ensure that developers and distributors of alternative Android-based operating systems who have no contractual relationship with Alphabet are able to access all interoperability solutions on the same technical terms as developers operating within Google's standard contractual ecosystem."

We urge the Commission to amend Footnote 5 accordingly: We draw the Commission's attention to footnote 5 of the Annex, which defines "Google Android mobile device" as "all mobile devices that Alphabet certified as a certified Android device or a Google Play supported device." This definition is in itself problematic for alternative Android Distributions' users and developers, as it potentially excludes devices running alternative Android distributions from the scope of the decision. The Commission should clarify, in the final text of the decision, that the interoperability obligations apply to all devices capable of running Android-based operating systems, regardless of whether those devices are certified by Alphabet or carry Google Play certification. A definition of scope that relies on Alphabet's certification status allows Alphabet to determine who

falls within the protection of the decision, which is precisely the kind of self-referential control the DMA is designed to remove.

Equal effectiveness and free-of-charge

Paragraphs 139 – Access must be workable without prerequisite commercial agreements

Paragraph 139 requires interoperability solutions to be "technically sound, stable, and workable in practice without unnecessary hurdles." As currently drafted, this does not address a specific and foreseeable barrier: requiring developers to hold a Google account or sign a developer programme or contribution agreement with Alphabet as a precondition for accessing the interoperability solutions.

This is not a theoretical concern. Account and agreement requirements are standard instruments through which platform operators condition access to technical resources, and they are particularly damaging here because they exclude an entire class of legitimate beneficiaries by design. Developers and distributors of alternative Android-based operating systems have deliberately structured their work outside Google's contractual ecosystem. For them, a requirement to hold a Google account or sign any agreement with Alphabet is not an administrative formality, it is a structural barrier that cannot be overcome without compromising the independence that defines their projects and their commutativity in regards to Google's Android.

Paragraph 139 must be amended to explicitly prohibit conditioning access on accounts or agreements with Alphabet:

The Commission should amend paragraph 139 to incorporate the following:

"Alphabet shall make all interoperability solutions accessible in a manner that is technically sound, stable, and workable in practice for third parties without

unnecessary hurdles. This prohibits Alphabet from conditioning access to any interoperability solution, or to any technical resource necessary to implement it, on the holding of a Google account of any kind or on the signing of any commercial, contribution, or developer programme agreement with Alphabet or any of its affiliates."

Paragraph 145 – Free of charge: no bypassing of effective access conditions

Paragraph 145 requires Alphabet to provide interoperability solutions free of charge and prohibits indirect fees. As currently drafted, this does not address a specific circumvention mechanism: requiring developers to hold a Google account or sign a developer programme or contribution agreement as a precondition for access.

These requirements are a form of indirect charging. A Google account carries obligations including submission to Google's terms of service and data collection. A developer programme or contribution agreement might carry further obligations on permitted uses, permitted integrations, and conditions under which access may be withdrawn.

For developers and distributors of alternative Android-based operating systems, the cost is higher still. These developers have structured their projects to avoid any relationship with Alphabet. An account or agreement imposes the loss of the independence that defines their work and makes them a genuine competitive alternative to Google's own Android distribution.

Paragraph 145 must be amended to explicitly prohibit accounts and developer agreements as instruments of indirect charging:

The Commission should amend paragraph 145 to incorporate the following:

"Alphabet shall provide all interoperability solutions and all technical resources necessary to implement them free of charge, irrespective of the beneficiary,

app, service, product, or use case. Alphabet shall not charge any fees indirectly for any of the measures set out in this Annex. Indirect charging includes conditioning access on the holding of a Google account of any kind or on the signing of any commercial, contribution, or developer programme agreement with Alphabet or any of its affiliates."